

Uncovering Mental Health Stigma with Digital Information-Seeking Behavioral Patterns in Mexico

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Objectives: To determine the patterns that emerge in digital mental health information-seeking behaviors (DMHISB) in Mexico in order to reduce mental health stigma and improve access to mental health care.

Background: According to the British Journal of Psychiatry, around 16% of people suffer from mental disorders such as anxiety, depression, and substance abuse, exacerbating Mexico's mental health crisis. Existing research has investigated the factors that elevate the prevalence of mental illness in Mexico, such as treatment barriers, environmental conditions, and poverty. However, there is little research exploring how mental health stigma influences digital information-seeking behaviors on anxiety, depression, and substance abuse. Understanding patterns in search queries could help inform future efforts to reduce mental health stigma and improve access to mental health care.

Methods: To evaluate information-seeking behaviors, we entered the following search terms into Google Trends: *stigma/estigma*, *depression/depresión*, *anxiety/ansiedad*, and *substance abuse/abuso de sustancias* (exactly as written). We performed an intra-language comparison examining web search patterns in Mexico over the previous decade (1/01/15 - 1/01/25). Additionally, we performed an inter-language analysis individually comparing each term's web search popularity while keeping all other variables constant.

Results: The intra-language analysis revealed the highest average relative search interest (ARSI) was 'Depression' (English) (M = 64, SD = 10) which reached peak popularity in July 2024, and 'ansiedad' (Spanish) at (M = 54, SD = 25) peaking in August 2022. Comparing all terms in the inter-language analysis, the ARSI's and SD's are as follows: 'Depresión' (M = 28, SD = 18), 'depression' (M = 5, SD = 1), 'estigma' (M = 42, SD = 11), 'stigma' (M = 16, SD = 6), 'ansiedad' (M = 54, SD = 25), 'anxiety' (M = 2, SD = 1), 'abuso de sustancias' (M = 42, SD = 22), and 'substance abuse' (M = 7, SD = 8). Standard errors ranged from ± 0.06 (anxiety) to ± 2.24 (ansiedad).

Conclusions: During 1/15/15 - 1/01/25, search popularity for 'anxiety' and 'ansiedad' rose near the end relative to other terms. Since the peaks occurred recently, this may reflect there is a heightened interest in understanding anxiety as a mental health issue, implying a potential need to increase treatment accessibility and address negative societal perceptions on mental illness.

Keyword 1: Digital Behavior

Keyword 2: Mental Disorders

Keyword 3: Health Stigma

Keyword 4: Mexico

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